

Operators Based On Multiple Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Sets

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Abstract: In this study, as a generalized form of multiple valued neutrosophic numbers and neutrosophic quadruple numbers, multiple generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers and sets are defined and their basic properties are given. Thus, a new structure is obtained in which multi-valued neutrosophic sets and neutrosophic quadruple sets are used together. Also, optimistic union, pessimistic union, average union, pessimistic intersection, optimistic intersection, average intersection operators are defined for multiple generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruples. Thus, multiple generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple sets were made usable in decision-making applications. Researchers can obtain more objective results in decision making applications by using these operators.

Keywords: Multi-valued Neutrosophic Number, Multiple Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Numbers, Multiple Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Sets, Generalized Set-Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Number

1. Introduction

Smarandache defined neutrosophic sets (NS) [1] in 1998. A neutrosophic structure is generally represented as (T, I, F) . In this notation, T is defined as the degree of membership, F as the degree of non-membership and I as the degree of indeterminacy, and these three components are given independently. This facilitates the mathematical description of uncertainties. It has found its place in the application areas in many different disciplines. Therefore, researchers have been conducting studies on decision-making structures in engineering, health services, data mining, cyber security, social sciences and many other fields. Şahin et al. defined metric spaces and normed spaces for neutrosophic numbers [2] in 2023. Miranda et al. measured the effectiveness of an indigenous knowledge-inspired training program for forest management applied to forest engineering students at the National University of Central Peru using neutrosophic 2-tuples [3]. Alqazzaz and Sallam studied the evaluation of sustainable waste valuation using treesoft set with neutrosophic nets [4]. Jdid and Smarandache worked on neutrosophic vision for decision making under the expected opportunity loss criterion (NEOL) risk [5]. Bedirhanoglu and Atlas studied production planning with fuzzy neutrosophic multi-objective optimization technique [6]. Chen et al. studied logarithmic similarity measurement of neutrosophic Z-number sets for undergraduate teaching quality assessment [7]. El-Massry et al. obtained on augmenting artificial intelligence techniques with soft computation of neutrosophic theory in mysterious conditions for plant diseases [8]. Vergara et al.

studied the use of logistic regression, ambiguous likert scales and similarity measures for insightful analysis of child labor, informality and poverty in Ecuador [9]. Surya et al. studied a neutrosophic inventory system [10] for perishable goods with price-dependent demand. Obbineni et al. studied neutrosophic cognitive maps for clinical decision making in mental health care, a unified learning approach [11]. Farag et al. worked on the integration between bioinformatics algorithms and neutrosophic theory [12]. Salama et al. performed a comparative study for medical image quality enhancement, leukemia detection and classification using neutrosophic fuzzy domain and multilevel enhancement transforms [13]. El-Henawy et al. worked on modeling the affected criteria in the unbalanced challenges of classifiers based on tree soft sets (TrSS) [14], supported by the uncertain nature of neutrosophic theory. Ram et al. introduced the concepts of categorical aspects [15] related to neutrosophic automata and inverse neutrosophic automata by studying various properties and relationships between neutrosophic automata, inverse neutrosophic automata and double neutrosophic automata. Salama et al. introduced a new and efficient approach for encoding and decoding of digital data by neutrosophic encoding and decoding algorithm for ASCII code system [16]. More recently, Sahin et al. have made research and definitions on quadruple neutrosophic theory and its applications [17] in 2023.

Chatterjee et al. defined a multivalued neutrosophic set (MVNS) [18] in 2015. Peng, J. J. et al. introduced MVNS operations, developed a comparison method and defined an approach for multi-criteria decision making problems using aggregation operators [19] in 2015. Peng, H. G. et al. Defined MVNS [20] in 2018, which allows accuracy-membership, uncertainty-membership and inaccuracy-membership to have a range of net values between zero and one, respectively.

Smarandache defined the neutrosophic quadruple set (NQS) [21] in 2015. In general, a neutrosophic quadruple number is of the form (k, IT, mI, nF) ($k, l, m, n \in \mathbb{R}$ or $\mathbb{C}$). The components T, I and F in this notation are components in neutrosophic logic. However, unlike the NS, NQS has a known part (k) and an unknown part ((IT, mI, nF)). Therefore, NQS is a new type of set that also includes NS. In addition, Şahin and Kargın defined set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers (SVNQN) [22] in 2019. Unlike neutrosophic quadruple numbers, in set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers, k, l, m, n are used as sets instead of real or complex numbers. That is, a set-valued neutrosophic quadruple number (SVNQN) over a set A is of the form (K, LT, MI, NF) ($K, L, M, N \in P(A)$, where $P(A)$ is the power set of A). Şahin et al. defined generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers (GSVNQN) [23] in 2020. Thanks to this new structure, the NQS theory has become available in the field of applications. Kargın et al. In 2021, Kargın et al. studied the generalized hamming similarity measure based on neutrosophic quadruple numbers and its applications to legal sciences [24]. Şahin and Kargın defined interval generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple sets [25] in 2022. A new structure was obtained by using interval neutrosophic sets and generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple sets together. Sahin et al. defined Pythagorean neutrosophic quadruple numbers and set-valued Pythagorean neutrosophic quadruple numbers [26] in 2022. Kargın and Şahin defined neutrosophic triplet normed spaces [27] in 2023, based on set-valued neutrosophic quadruple numbers. Sahin et al. defined interval generalized set-valued neutrosophic quadruple graphs [28] in 2023. Şahin and Kargın defined interval generalized set-valued Pythagorean neutrosophic quadruple numbers [29] in 2023.

In this study, In The Preliminaries Section, the basic definitions and properties to be used in this study are given by mentioning NQS, MGNS, SVNQN and SVNQS, known-unknown part, membership degrees, indeterminacy and non-membership degrees. In the research and findings section, we define the MGSVNQN and MGSVNQS and the main features of these new concepts are given. Thus, we have obtained a new structure for NQS, MVS. Optimistic union, pessimistic union, average union, pessimistic intersection, optimistic intersection, average intersection operators were

defined for MGSVNQS. Sample sets from daily life were created and operations were performed on the sets for all the aforementioned properties and definitions. In The Conclusion Section, the results obtained in the study and suggestions for future studies are presented.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1:[5] Let X be a universal set. For $\forall \tilde{d}_\beta \in X$,

$$0 \leq T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}} + I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}} + F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}} \leq 3$$

$$T^{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0, 1] , I^{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0, 1] \text{ and } F^{\tilde{K}}: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

With functions, a $\tilde{K}$ single-valued NS on X ; It is defined as

$$\tilde{K} = \{(\tilde{d}_\beta, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}}, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}}, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}}) : \tilde{d}_\beta \in X\}.$$

$T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}}, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}}, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}}$ are the degree of truth, indeterminacy and falsity of $\tilde{d}_\beta \in X$, respectively.

Definition 2.2: [6] Let E be an universal set, a MVNS $\tilde{K}$ over the set E can be defined as follows.

For $\forall x_j \in E; i=1, \dots, p$ and $\beta = 1, \dots, n$;

$$\tilde{K} = \{(\tilde{d}_\beta, (T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p}), (I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p}), (F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p})) : \tilde{d}_\beta \in E\}$$

$$T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p} : E \rightarrow [0, 1] ,$$

$$I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p} : E \rightarrow [0, 1],$$

$$F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p} : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

It is also,

$$0 \leq T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^i} + I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^i} + F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^i} \leq 3$$

$$(T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, T_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p}), (I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, I_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p}) \text{ and } (F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^1}, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^2}, \dots, F_{(\tilde{d}_\beta)}^{\tilde{K}^p})$$

The degree of truth, the degree of indeterminacy, the degree of falsity, respectively.

Definition 2.3:[7] Let N be a set and let $P(N)$ be the power set of N . $\tilde{K}^N$ SVNQN is of the form

$$\tilde{K}^N = (\tilde{K}_{\beta_1}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_2} T_{\tilde{K}_{\beta_2}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_3} I_{\tilde{K}_{\beta_3}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_4} F_{\tilde{K}_{\beta_4}}).$$

Here T, I and F are the degree of membership, degree of uncertainty and degree of non-membership as in the neutrosophic theory, respectively and $\tilde{K}_{\beta_1}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_2}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_3}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_4} \in P(N)$. Also, a SVNQS is defined such that

$$\tilde{K} = \{(\tilde{K}_{\beta_1}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_2} T_{\tilde{K}_{\beta_2}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_3} I_{\tilde{K}_{\beta_3}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_4} F_{\tilde{K}_{\beta_4}}) : \tilde{K}_{\beta_1}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_2}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_3}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_4} \in P(N)\}$$

Where, similar to neutrosophic quadruple sets,

$$\tilde{K}_{\beta_1}$$

is called the known part and

$$(\tilde{K}_{\beta_2} T_{\beta_2}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_3} I_{\beta_3}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_4} F_{\beta_4}^{\tilde{K}})$$

is called the unknown part.

Definition 2.4: [9] Let X be a set and let P(X) be the power set of X. $\tilde{K}_i$ set of a GSVNQN form

$$\tilde{K} = \{(\tilde{K}_{\beta_{1i}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{2i}} T_{\beta_{2i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{3i}} I_{\beta_{3i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{4i}} F_{\beta_{4i}}^{\tilde{K}}) : \tilde{K}_{\beta_{1i}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{2i}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{3i}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{4i}} \in P(X); i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$$

$T_{\beta_{2i}}^{\tilde{K}}$, $I_{\beta_{3i}}^{\tilde{K}}$ and $F_{\beta_{4i}}^{\tilde{K}}$ are the usual neutrosophic logic tools. Also, a GSVNQS is defined such that

$$\tilde{K}_i^N = (\tilde{K}_{\beta_{1i}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{2i}} T_{\beta_{2i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{3i}} I_{\beta_{3i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{4i}} F_{\beta_{4i}}^{\tilde{K}}).$$

Where, a GSVNQN representing an entity that can be a number, an idea, an object, etc. For a GSVNQN $(\tilde{K}_{\beta_{1i}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{2i}} T_{\beta_{2i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{3i}} I_{\beta_{3i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{4i}} F_{\beta_{4i}}^{\tilde{K}})$

$$\tilde{K}_{\beta_{1i}}$$

is called the known part and

$$(\tilde{K}_{\beta_{2i}} T_{\beta_{2i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{3i}} I_{\beta_{3i}}^{\tilde{K}}, \tilde{K}_{\beta_{4i}} F_{\beta_{4i}}^{\tilde{K}})$$

is called the unknown part.

We can also show that the GSVNQN consisting of GSVNQS

$$\tilde{K} = \{\tilde{K}_i^N; i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$$

3. Research and Findings

Definition 3.1: Let E be universal set and P(E) be power set of E. $\tilde{C}$ MGSVNS over the set E is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{C} = \{ & \{(M_{1(x_i)}^1, M_{1(x_i)}^2, M_{1(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{1(x_i)}^n), (M_{2(x_i)}^1, M_{2(x_i)}^2, M_{2(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{2(x_i)}^n) (T_{M_2(x_i)}^1, T_{M_2(x_i)}^2, T_{M_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{M_2(x_i)}^n), \\ & (M_{3(x_i)}^1, M_{3(x_i)}^2, M_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{3(x_i)}^n) (I_{M_3(x_i)}^1, I_{M_3(x_i)}^2, I_{M_3(x_i)}^3, \dots, I_{M_3(x_i)}^n), (M_{4(x_i)}^1, M_{4(x_i)}^2, M_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{4(x_i)}^n) \\ & (F_{M_4(x_i)}^1, F_{M_4(x_i)}^2, F_{M_4(x_i)}^3, \dots, F_{M_4(x_i)}^n)\} : M_{1(x_i)}^n, M_{2(x_i)}^n, M_{3(x_i)}^n, M_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p$$

$$T_{M_2}^1, T_{M_2}^2, T_{M_2}^3, \dots, T_{M_2}^n : E \rightarrow [0,1],$$

$$I_{M_3}^1, I_{M_3}^2, I_{M_3}^3, \dots, I_{M_3}^n : E \rightarrow [0,1],$$

$$F_{M_4}^1, F_{M_4}^2, F_{M_4}^3, \dots, F_{M_4}^n : E \rightarrow [0,1]$$

$$0 \leq \dots, T_{M_2(x_i)}^n + I_{M_3(x_i)}^n + F_{M_4(x_i)}^n \leq 3$$

and

$$T_{M_2}^1(x_j), T_{M_2}^2(x_j), T_{M_2}^3(x_j), \dots, T_{M_2}^n(x_j),$$

$$I_{M_3}^1(x_j), I_{M_3}^2(x_j), I_{M_3}^3(x_j), \dots, I_{M_3}^n(x_j),$$

$$F_{M_4}^1(x_j), F_{M_4}^2(x_j), F_{M_4}^3(x_j), \dots, F_{M_4}^n(x_j)$$

degrees of truth, degrees of indeterminacy, degrees of falsity, respectively.

Note 3.2: From Definition 2.2 and Definition 2.4, MGSVNSs satisfy the conditions both GSVNS and MVNSs. Also, in the MGSVNS, p is the number of elements of the set and n is the number of components of each element.

Definition 3.3: Let

$$\check{C} = \{ \{ (M_{1(x_i)}^1, M_{1(x_i)}^2, M_{1(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{1(x_i)}^n), (M_{2(x_i)}^1, M_{2(x_i)}^2, M_{2(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{2(x_i)}^n) (T_{M_2(x_i)}^1, T_{M_2(x_i)}^2, T_{M_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{M_2(x_i)}^n),$$

$$(M_{3(x_i)}^1, M_{3(x_i)}^2, M_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{3(x_i)}^n) (I_{M_3(x_i)}^1, I_{M_3(x_i)}^2, I_{M_3(x_i)}^3, \dots, I_{M_3(x_i)}^n), (M_{4(x_i)}^1, M_{4(x_i)}^2, M_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{4(x_i)}^n)$$

$$(F_{M_4(x_i)}^1, F_{M_4(x_i)}^2, F_{M_4(x_i)}^3, \dots, F_{M_4(x_i)}^n) \} : M_{1(x_i)}^n, M_{2(x_i)}^n, M_{3(x_i)}^n, M_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \}.$$

be a MGSVNS and let P(E) be the power set of E. A MGSVNQN $\check{C}$ is defined as

$$\check{C}_1 = \{ (M_{1S_{x_1}^1}, M_{1S_{x_1}^2}, \dots, M_{1S_{x_1}^n}), (M_{2S_{x_1}^1}, M_{2S_{x_1}^2}, \dots, M_{2S_{x_1}^n}) (T_{S_{x_1}^1}(x_1), T_{S_{x_1}^2}(x_1), \dots, T_{S_{x_1}^n}(x_1)),$$

$$(M_{3S_{x_1}^1}, M_{3S_{x_1}^2}, \dots, M_{3S_{x_1}^n}) (I_{S_{x_1}^1}(x_1), I_{S_{x_1}^2}(x_1), \dots, I_{S_{x_1}^n}(x_1)), (M_{4S_{x_1}^1}, M_{4S_{x_1}^2}, \dots, M_{4S_{x_1}^n})$$

$$(F_{S_{x_1}^1}(x_1), F_{S_{x_1}^2}(x_1), \dots, F_{S_{x_1}^n}(x_1)) \}.$$

Where, i=1; n=1, ..., p.

As in NQN, an MVNQN representing an entity that can be a number, an idea, an object, etc. For

$$(M_{1S_{x_1}}, M_{2S_{x_1}}, M_{3S_{x_1}}, M_{4S_{x_1}})$$

$(M_{1S_{x_1}})$ is called the known part and

$$(M_{2S_{x_1}}, M_{3S_{x_1}}, M_{4S_{x_1}})$$

is called the unknown part.

MGSVNQS can also be represented in the form of

$$\check{C} = \{\check{C}_i ; i = 1,2, \dots, j\}.$$

Example 3.4: $\check{C} = \{\text{Biology, Geography, Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge, Literature, Geometry, English, Chemistry, Mathematics}\}$

Let the set represent different textbooks studied in a month. For four consecutive weeks of a student in a month, we represent the lessons solved by H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 GSVNQS. In addition, let $\check{C}_{n_1}, \check{C}_{n_2}, \check{C}_{n_3}, \check{C}_{n_4}, \check{C}_{n_5}$ be the MGSVNQN representation of the courses with questions solved on Monday, Tuesday, Wednesday, Thursday and Friday, respectively. (Biology 'B', Geography 'Ge', Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge 'D', Literature 'E', Geometry 'G', English 'I', Chemistry 'C', Mathematics 'M' will be expressed as abbreviations in the sets $\check{C}_{n_1}, \check{C}_{n_2}, \check{C}_{n_3}, \check{C}_{n_4}, \check{C}_{n_5}$)

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1 = & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Monday}_1 = \{\{\text{Mathematics, Geometry}\}, \{\text{Religion, Literature}\}(0.3), \\ \{\text{English, Geography}\}(0.5), \{\text{Biology}\}(0.1)\} \\ \text{Tuesday}_1 = \{\{\text{English}\}, \{\text{Chemistry, Literature}\}(0.2), \\ \{\text{Mathematics, Geometry}\}(0.6), \{\text{D.k, Biology}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Wednesday}_1 = \{\{\text{Biology, Geography, English}\}, \{\text{Literature}\}(0.3), \\ \{\text{Geometry, Religious Studies}\}(0.5), \{\text{Mathematics}\}(0.2)\} \\ \text{Thursday}_1 = \{\{\text{Mathematics}\}, \{\text{Literature, Biology}\}(0.3), \\ \{\text{Religion, English}\}(0.4), \{\text{Geography}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Friday}_1 = \{\{\text{Geometry, English}\}, \{\text{Geography, Maths}\}(0.6), \\ \{\text{Chemistry, Religious Studies}\}(0.2), \{\text{Literature, Biology}\}(0.3)\} \end{array} \right\} \\
 H_2 = & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Monday}_2 = \{\{\text{Religion, Literature}\}, \{\text{Chemistry}\}(0.2), \\ \{\text{Mathematics, Geometry}\}(0.5), \{\text{Geography, Biology}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Tuesday}_2 = \{\{\text{English, Maths}\}, \{\text{Geography, Geometry}\}(0.4), \\ \{\text{Religious Studies}\}(0.3), \{\text{Literature, Chemistry}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Wednesday}_2 = \{\{\text{Geography, English}\}, \{\text{Literature, Maths}\}(0.5), \\ \{\text{Geometry, Religious Studies}\}(0.3), \{\text{Biology}\}(0.2)\} \\ \text{Thursday}_2 = \{\{\text{Geometry, Maths}\}, \{\text{Geography, Chemistry, Biology}\}(0.7), \\ \{\text{Religious Studies}\}(0.2), \{\text{English}\}(0.1)\} \\ \text{Friday}_2 = \{\{\text{Chemistry}\}, \{\text{Mathematics}\}(0.3), \\ \{\text{Biology, Literature}\}(0.4), \{\text{Religion, English}\}(0.3)\} \end{array} \right\} \\
 H_3 = & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Monday}_3 = \{\{\text{Mathematics}\}, \{\text{Geometry}\}(0.1), \\ \{\text{Chemistry, Religious Studies}\}(0.3), \{\text{Literature, Geography}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Tuesday}_3 = \{\{\text{Religion, Geometry}\}, \{\text{English}\}(0.3), \\ \{\text{Chemistry}\}(0.1), \{\text{Literature, Geography, Mathematics}\}(0.6)\} \\ \text{Wednesday}_3 = \{\{\text{Literature, Chemistry, Biology}\}, \{\text{Mathematics, Geometry}\}(0.5), \\ \{\text{Religious Studies}\}(0.2), \{\text{English}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Thursday}_3 = \{\{\text{Chemistry}\}, \{\text{Mathematics, Geometry}\}(0.5), \\ \{\text{Religion K.}\}(0.3), \{\text{Biology}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Friday}_3 = \{\{\text{English}\}, \{\text{Literature, Geometry}\}(0.3), \\ \{\text{Chemistry, Religious Studies}\}(0.1), \{\text{Geography, Mathematics, Biology}\}(0.6)\} \end{array} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_4 &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Monday}_4 = \{\{\text{English, Geometry}\}, \{\text{Chemistry, Literature}\}(0.4), \\ \quad \{\text{Biology}\}(0.4), \{\text{Mathematics, Geography}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Tuesday}_4 = \{\{\text{Biology, Maths, Geometry}\}, \{\text{Literature}\}(0.1), \\ \quad \{\text{Chemistry}\}(0.7), \{\text{Geography, English, Chemistry}\}(0.2)\} \\ \text{Wednesday}_4 = \{\{\text{Geography}\}, \{\text{Geometry, Chemistry, Biology}\}(0.8), \\ \quad \{\text{English, Maths}\}(0.1), \{\text{Religious Studies}\}(0.1)\} \\ \text{Thursday}_4 = \{\{\text{Mathematics, Chemistry, Geometry}\}, \{\text{Literature}\}(0.2), \\ \quad \{\text{Geography, Religious Studies}\}(0.5), \{\text{Biology}\}(0.3)\} \\ \text{Friday}_4 = \{\{\text{Geometry}\}, \{\text{English, Maths}\}(0.5), \\ \quad \{\text{Chemistry, Religious Studies}\}(0.3), \{\text{Literature, Biology}\}(0.2)\} \end{array} \right\} \\
 \check{C}_{n_1} &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{M, G\}, \{R, L\}, \{M\}, \{E, Ge\}), (\{R, L\}, \{C\}, \{G\}\{C, L\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.4), \\ (\{E, Ge\}, \{M, G\}, \{C, R\}, \{B\})(0.5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4), (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.1, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3) \end{array} \right\} \\
 \check{C}_{n_2} &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{E\}, \{E, M\}, \{R, G\}, \{B, M, G\}), (\{C, L\}, \{Ge, G\}, \{E\}, \{L\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.1), \\ (\{M, G\}, \{R\}, \{C\}, \{C\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.7), (\{R, B\}, \{L, C\}, \{L, Ge, M\}, \{Ge, E, C\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) \end{array} \right\} \\
 \check{C}_{n_3} &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{B, Ge, E\}, \{Ge, E\}, \{L, C, B\}, \{Ge\}), (\{L\}, \{L, M\}, \{M, G\}, \{G, C, B\})(0.3, 0.5, 0.5, 0.8), \\ (\{G, R\}, \{G, R\}, \{R\}, \{E, M\})(0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), (\{M\}, \{B\}, \{E\}, \{R\})(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1) \end{array} \right\} \\
 \check{C}_{n_4} &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{G, M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, C\}, \{M, C, G\}), (\{L, B\}, \{Ge, C, B\}, \{M, G\}, \{L\})(0.3, 0.7, 0.5, 0.2), \\ (\{R, E\}, \{R\}, \{R\}, \{Ge, R\})(0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5), (\{Ge\}, \{E\}, \{B\}, \{B\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.3) \end{array} \right\} \\
 \check{C}_{n_5} &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{G, E\}, \{C\}, \{E\}, \{G\}), (\{Ge, M\}, \{M\}, \{L, G\}, \{E, M\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.3, 0.5), \\ (\{C, R\}, \{B, L\}, \{C, R\}, \{C, R\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.3), (\{L, B\}, \{R, E\}, \{Ge, M, B\}, \{L, B\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) \end{array} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, if we represent the month with these four weeks as a single set, we obtain $\check{C}_n$ MGSVNQS such that

$$\check{C}_n = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{M, G\}, \{R, L\}, \{M\}, \{E, Ge\}), (\{R, L\}, \{C\}, \{G\}\{C, L\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.4), \\ (\{E, Ge\}, \{M, G\}, \{C, R\}, \{B\})(0.5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4), (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.1, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3), \\ (\{E\}, \{E, M\}, \{R, G\}, \{B, M, G\}), (\{C, L\}, \{Ge, G\}, \{E\}, \{L\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.1), \\ (\{M, G\}, \{R\}, \{C\}, \{C\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.7), (\{R, B\}, \{L, C\}, \{L, Ge, M\}, \{Ge, E, C\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2), \\ (\{B, Ge, E\}, \{Ge, E\}, \{L, C, B\}, \{Ge\}), (\{L\}, \{L, M\}, \{M, G\}, \{G, C, B\})(0.3, 0.5, 0.5, 0.8), \\ (\{G, R\}, \{G, R\}, \{R\}, \{E, M\})(0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), (\{M\}, \{B\}, \{E\}, \{R\})(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1), \\ (\{G, M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, C\}, \{M, C, G\}), (\{L, B\}, \{Ge, C, B\}, \{M, G\}, \{L\})(0.3, 0.7, 0.5, 0.2), \\ (\{R, E\}, \{R\}, \{R\}, \{Ge, R\})(0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5), (\{Ge\}, \{E\}, \{B\}, \{B\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.3), \\ (\{G, E\}, \{C\}, \{E\}, \{G\}), (\{Ge, M\}, \{M\}, \{L, G\}, \{E, M\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.3, 0.5), \\ (\{C, R\}, \{B, L\}, \{C, R\}, \{C, R\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.3), (\{L, B\}, \{R, E\}, \{Ge, M, B\}, \{L, B\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) \end{array} \right\}$$

Where, thanks to $\check{C}_n$ MGSVNQS, the sets $\check{C}_{n_1}, \check{C}_{n_2}, \check{C}_{n_3}, \check{C}_{n_4}, \check{C}_{n_5}$ were expressed as a single set.

Definition 3.5: Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 M^{\check{C}} &= \{((M_1^1(x_i), M_1^2(x_i), M_1^3(x_i), \dots, M_1^n(x_i)), (M_2^1(x_i), M_2^2(x_i), M_2^3(x_i), \dots, M_2^n(x_i))) \\
 &\quad (T_{M_2(x_i)}^1, T_{M_2(x_i)}^2, T_{M_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{M_2(x_i)}^n), (M_3^1(x_i), M_3^2(x_i), M_3^3(x_i), \dots, M_3^n(x_i)) (I_{M_3(x_i)}^1, I_{M_3(x_i)}^2, I_{M_3(x_i)}^3, \dots, I_{M_3(x_i)}^n)) \\
 &\quad (M_4^1(x_i), M_4^2(x_i), M_4^3(x_i), \dots, M_4^n(x_i)) (F_{M_4(x_i)}^1, F_{M_4(x_i)}^2, F_{M_4(x_i)}^3, \dots, F_{M_4(x_i)}^n)) : M_1^n(x_i), M_2^n(x_i), M_3^n(x_i), M_4^n(x_i) \in P(E)\}
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$N^{\check{C}} = \{((N_1^1(x_i), N_1^2(x_i), N_1^3(x_i), \dots, N_1^n(x_i)), (N_2^1(x_i), N_2^2(x_i), N_2^3(x_i), \dots, N_2^n(x_i)))$$

$$\left(T_{N_2(x_i)}^1, T_{N_2(x_i)}^2, T_{N_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{N_2(x_i)}^n \right), \left(N_{3(x_i)}^1, N_{3(x_i)}^2, N_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{3(x_i)}^n \right) \left(I_{N_3(x_i)}^1, I_{N_3(x_i)}^2, I_{N_3(x_i)}^3, \dots, I_{N_3(x_i)}^n \right) \\ \left(N_{4(x_i)}^1, N_{4(x_i)}^2, N_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{4(x_i)}^n \right) \left(F_{N_4(x_i)}^1, F_{N_4(x_i)}^2, F_{N_4(x_i)}^3, \dots, F_{N_4(x_i)}^n \right) \left. \vphantom{\left(T_{N_2(x_i)}^1, T_{N_2(x_i)}^2, T_{N_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{N_2(x_i)}^n \right)} \right\} : N_{1(x_i)}^n, N_{2(x_i)}^n, N_{3(x_i)}^n, N_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \}$$

be two MGSVNQSs.

- i. If the following conditions are satisfied, we say that $M^{\check{c}}$ is a subset of $N^{\check{c}}$ and denote $M^{\check{c}} \subset N^{\check{c}}$.

$$M_1^n(x_i) \subset N_1^n(x_i)$$

$$M_2^n(x_i) \subset N_2^n(x_i)$$

$$M_3^n(x_i) \subset N_3^n(x_i)$$

$$M_4^n(x_i) \subset N_4^n(x_i)$$

and

$$T_{M_2(x_i)}^n \leq T_{N_2(x_i)}^n$$

$$I_{M_3(x_i)}^n \geq I_{N_3(x_i)}^n$$

$$F_{M_4(x_i)}^n \geq F_{N_4(x_i)}^n$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$

- ii. If the following conditions are satisfied, $M^{\check{c}}$ is equal to $N^{\check{c}}$ and is denoted as $M^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}}$.

$$M_1^n(x_i) = N_1^n(x_i)$$

$$M_2^n(x_i) = N_2^n(x_i)$$

$$M_3^n(x_i) = N_3^n(x_i)$$

$$M_4^n(x_i) = N_4^n(x_i)$$

and

$$T_{M_2(x_i)}^n = T_{N_2(x_i)}^n$$

$$I_{M_3(x_i)}^n = I_{N_3(x_i)}^n$$

$$F_{M_4(x_i)}^n = F_{N_4(x_i)}^n$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$

Definition 3.6: Let

$$M^{\check{c}} = \{ ((M_{1(x_i)}^1, M_{1(x_i)}^2, M_{1(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{1(x_i)}^n), (M_{2(x_i)}^1, M_{2(x_i)}^2, M_{2(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{2(x_i)}^n) \}$$

$$\left(T_{M_2(x_i)}^1, T_{M_2(x_i)}^2, T_{M_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{M_2(x_i)}^n \right), (M_{3(x_i)}^1, M_{3(x_i)}^2, M_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{3(x_i)}^n) \left(I_{M_3(x_i)}^1, I_{M_3(x_i)}^2, I_{M_3(x_i)}^3, \dots, I_{M_3(x_i)}^n \right) \\ \left(M_{4(x_i)}^1, M_{4(x_i)}^2, M_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, M_{4(x_i)}^n \right) \left(F_{M_4(x_i)}^1, F_{M_4(x_i)}^2, F_{M_4(x_i)}^3, \dots, F_{M_4(x_i)}^n \right) : M_{1(x_i)}^n, M_{2(x_i)}^n, M_{3(x_i)}^n, M_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \}$$

and

$$N^{\tilde{c}} = \{ \left((N_{1(x_i)}^1, N_{1(x_i)}^2, N_{1(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{1(x_i)}^n), (N_{2(x_i)}^1, N_{2(x_i)}^2, N_{2(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{2(x_i)}^n) \right. \\ \left. \left(T_{N_2(x_i)}^1, T_{N_2(x_i)}^2, T_{N_2(x_i)}^3, \dots, T_{N_2(x_i)}^n \right), (N_{3(x_i)}^1, N_{3(x_i)}^2, N_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{3(x_i)}^n) \right) \left(I_{N_3(x_i)}^1, I_{N_3(x_i)}^2, I_{N_3(x_i)}^3, \dots, I_{N_3(x_i)}^n \right) \\ \left. \left(N_{4(x_i)}^1, N_{4(x_i)}^2, N_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{4(x_i)}^n \right) \left(F_{N_4(x_i)}^1, F_{N_4(x_i)}^2, F_{N_4(x_i)}^3, \dots, F_{N_4(x_i)}^n \right) \right\} : N_{1(x_i)}^n, N_{2(x_i)}^n, N_{3(x_i)}^n, N_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \}$$

be two MGSVNQSs.

i. Average $\cup$ operation for $M^{\tilde{c}}$ and $N^{\tilde{c}}$ is defined as

$$M^{\tilde{c}} \cup_A N^{\tilde{c}} = \{ \left((M, N)_{1(x_i)}^1, (M, N)_{1(x_i)}^2, \dots, (M, N)_{1(x_i)}^n \right), \\ \left((M, N)_{2(x_i)}^1, (M, N)_{2(x_i)}^2, \dots, (M, N)_{2(x_i)}^n \right) \left(T_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^1, T_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^2, \dots, T_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^n \right), \\ \left((M, N)_{3(x_i)}^1, (M, N)_{3(x_i)}^2, \dots, (M, N)_{3(x_i)}^n \right) \left(I_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^1, I_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^2, \dots, I_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^n \right), \\ \left((M, N)_{4(x_i)}^1, (M, N)_{4(x_i)}^2, \dots, (M, N)_{4(x_i)}^n \right) \left(F_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^1, F_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^2, \dots, F_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^n \right) \right\}, \\ (M, N)_{1(x_i)}^n, (M, N)_{2(x_i)}^n, (M, N)_{3(x_i)}^n, (M, N)_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \}.$$

Where,

$$(M, N)_{1(x_i)}^n = M_1^n(x_i) \cup N_1^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)_{2(x_i)}^n = M_2^n(x_i) \cup N_2^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)_{3(x_i)}^n = M_3^n(x_i) \cup N_3^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)_{4(x_i)}^n = M_4^n(x_i) \cup N_4^n(x_i)$$

$$T_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}^n = \frac{T_{(M)_2(x_i)}^n + T_{(N)_2(x_i)}^n}{2}$$

$$I_{(M,N)_3(x_i)}^n = \frac{I_{(M)_3(x_i)}^n + I_{(N)_3(x_i)}^n}{2}$$

$$F_{(M,N)_4(x_i)}^n = \frac{F_{(M)_4(x_i)}^n + F_{(N)_4(x_i)}^n}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$$

ii. Average $\cap$ operation for $M^{\tilde{c}}$ and $N^{\tilde{c}}$ is defined as

$$M^{\tilde{c}} \cap_A N^{\tilde{c}} = \{ \left((M, N)_{1(x_i)}^1, (M, N)_{1(x_i)}^2, \dots, (M, N)_{1(x_i)}^n \right),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ((M, N)^1_2(x_i), (M, N)^2_2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_2(x_i)) (T^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, T^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}), \\
 & ((M, N)^1_3(x_i), (M, N)^2_3(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_3(x_i)) (I^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, I^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, I^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}), \\
 & ((M, N)^1_4(x_i), (M, N)^2_4(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_4(x_i)) (F^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, F^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, F^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}), \\
 & (M, N)^n_1(x_i), (M, N)^n_2(x_i), (M, N)^n_3(x_i), (M, N)^n_4(x_i) \in P(E)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Where,

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i) = M^n_1(x_i) \cap N^n_1(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_2(x_i) = M^n_2(x_i) \cap N^n_2(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = M^n_3(x_i) \cap N^n_3(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_4(x_i) = M^n_4(x_i) \cap N^n_4(x_i)$$

$$T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)} = \frac{T^n_{(M)_2(x_i)} + T^n_{(N)_2(x_i)}}{2}$$

$$I^n_{(M,N)_3(x_i)} = \frac{I^n_{(M)_3(x_i)} + I^n_{(N)_3(x_i)}}{2}$$

$$F^n_{(M,N)_4(x_i)} = \frac{F^n_{(M)_4(x_i)} + F^n_{(N)_4(x_i)}}{2}$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p$.

iii. Optimistic $\cup$ operation for $M^{\check{c}}$ and $N^{\check{c}}$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 M^{\check{c}} \cup_o N^{\check{c}} = \{ & ((M, N)^1_1(x_i), (M, N)^2_1(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_1(x_i)), \\
 & ((M, N)^1_2(x_i), (M, N)^2_2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_2(x_i)) (T^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, T^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}), \\
 & ((M, N)^1_3(x_i), (M, N)^2_3(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_3(x_i)) (I^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, I^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, I^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}), \\
 & ((M, N)^1_4(x_i), (M, N)^2_4(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_4(x_i)) (F^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, F^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, F^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}), \\
 & (M, N)^n_1(x_i), (M, N)^n_2(x_i), (M, N)^n_3(x_i), (M, N)^n_4(x_i) \in P(E)\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Where,

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i) = M^n_1(x_i) \cup N^n_1(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_2(x_i) = M^n_2(x_i) \cup N^n_2(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = M^n_3(x_i) \cup N^n_3(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_4(x_i) = M^n_4(x_i) \cup N^n_4(x_i)$$

$$T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)} = \max\{T^n_{(M)_2(x_i)}, T^n_{(N)_2(x_i)}\}$$

$$I_{(M,N)_3}^n(x_i) = \min \{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i), I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)\}$$

$$F_{(M,N)_4}^n(x_i) = \min \{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i), F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)\}$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$

iv. Optimistic $\cap$ operation for $M^{\check{c}}$ ve $N^{\check{c}}$ is defined as

$$M^{\check{c}} \cap_o N^{\check{c}} = \{((M, N)_1^1(x_i), (M, N)_1^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_1^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)_2^1(x_i), (M, N)_2^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_2^n(x_i)) (T_{(M,N)_2}^1(x_i), T_{(M,N)_2}^2(x_i), \dots, T_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)_3^1(x_i), (M, N)_3^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_3^n(x_i)) (I_{(M,N)_2}^1(x_i), I_{(M,N)_2}^2(x_i), \dots, I_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)_4^1(x_i), (M, N)_4^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_4^n(x_i)) (F_{(M,N)_2}^1(x_i), F_{(M,N)_2}^2(x_i), \dots, F_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i)),$$

$$(M, N)_1^n(x_i), (M, N)_2^n(x_i), (M, N)_3^n(x_i), (M, N)_4^n(x_i) \in P(E)\}.$$

Where,

$$(M, N)_1^n(x_i) = M_1^n(x_i) \cap N_1^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)_2^n(x_i) = M_2^n(x_i) \cap N_2^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)_3^n(x_i) = M_3^n(x_i) \cap N_3^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)_4^n(x_i) = M_4^n(x_i) \cap N_4^n(x_i)$$

$$T_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i) = \min \{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i), T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)\}$$

$$I_{(M,N)_3}^n(x_i) = \max \{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i), I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)\}$$

$$F_{(M,N)_4}^n(x_i) = \max \{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i), F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)\}$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$

v. Pessimistic $\cup$ operation for $M^{\check{c}}$ and $N^{\check{c}}$ is defined as

$$M^{\check{c}} \cup_p N^{\check{c}} = \{((M, N)_1^1(x_i), (M, N)_1^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_1^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)_2^1(x_i), (M, N)_2^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_2^n(x_i)) (T_{(M,N)_2}^1(x_i), T_{(M,N)_2}^2(x_i), \dots, T_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)_3^1(x_i), (M, N)_3^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_3^n(x_i)) (I_{(M,N)_2}^1(x_i), I_{(M,N)_2}^2(x_i), \dots, I_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)_4^1(x_i), (M, N)_4^2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)_4^n(x_i)) (F_{(M,N)_2}^1(x_i), F_{(M,N)_2}^2(x_i), \dots, F_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i)),$$

$$(M, N)_1^n(x_i), (M, N)_2^n(x_i), (M, N)_3^n(x_i), (M, N)_4^n(x_i) \in P(E)\}.$$

Where,

$$(M, N)_1^n(x_i) = M_1^n(x_i) \cup N_1^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_2(x_i) = M^n_2(x_i) \cup N^n_2(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = M^n_3(x_i) \cup N^n_3(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_4(x_i) = M^n_4(x_i) \cup N^n_4(x_i)$$

$$T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)=\min}\{T^n_{(M)_2(x_i)}, T^n_{(N)_2(x_i)}\}$$

$$I^n_{(M,N)_3(x_i)=\max}\{I^n_{(M)_3(x_i)}, I^n_{(N)_3(x_i)}\}$$

$$F^n_{(M,N)_4(x_i)=\max}\{F^n_{(M)_4(x_i)}, F^n_{(N)_4(x_i)}\}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$$

vi. Pessimistic $\cap$ operation for $M^{\check{c}}$ ve $N^{\check{c}}$ is defined as

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_p N^{\check{c}} = \{((M, N)^1_1(x_i), (M, N)^2_1(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_1(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N)^1_2(x_i), (M, N)^2_2(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_2(x_i)) (T^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, T^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}),$$

$$((M, N)^1_3(x_i), (M, N)^2_3(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_3(x_i)) (I^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, I^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, I^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}),$$

$$((M, N)^1_4(x_i), (M, N)^2_4(x_i), \dots, (M, N)^n_4(x_i)) (F^1_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, F^2_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}, \dots, F^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)}),$$

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i), (M, N)^n_2(x_i), (M, N)^n_3(x_i), (M, N)^n_4(x_i) \in P(E)\}.$$

Where,

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i) = M^n_1(x_i) \cap N^n_1(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_2(x_i) = M^n_2(x_i) \cap N^n_2(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = M^n_3(x_i) \cap N^n_3(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_4(x_i) = M^n_4(x_i) \cap N^n_4(x_i)$$

$$T^n_{(M,N)_2(x_i)=\min}\{T^n_{(M)_2(x_i)}, T^n_{(N)_2(x_i)}\}$$

$$I^n_{(M,N)_3(x_i)=\max}\{I^n_{(M)_3(x_i)}, I^n_{(N)_3(x_i)}\}$$

$$F^n_{(M,N)_4(x_i)=\max}\{F^n_{(M)_4(x_i)}, F^n_{(N)_4(x_i)}\}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$$

Properties 3.7: Let

$$M^{\check{c}} = \{((M^1_1(x_i), M^2_1(x_i), M^3_1(x_i), \dots, M^n_1(x_i)), (M^1_2(x_i), M^2_2(x_i), M^3_2(x_i), \dots, M^n_2(x_i))$$

$$(T^1_{M_2(x_i)}, T^2_{M_2(x_i)}, T^3_{M_2(x_i)}, \dots, T^n_{M_2(x_i)}), (M^1_3(x_i), M^2_3(x_i), M^3_3(x_i), \dots, M^n_3(x_i)) (I^1_{M_3(x_i)}, I^2_{M_3(x_i)}, I^3_{M_3(x_i)}, \dots, I^n_{M_3(x_i)})$$

$$(M^1_4(x_i), M^2_4(x_i), M^3_4(x_i), \dots, M^n_4(x_i)) (F^1_{M_4(x_i)}, F^2_{M_4(x_i)}, F^3_{M_4(x_i)}, \dots, F^n_{M_4(x_i)})\} : M^n_1(x_i), M^n_2(x_i), M^n_3(x_i), M^n_4(x_i) \in P(E)\},$$

$$N^{\check{c}} = \left\{ \left((N_{1(x_i)}^1, N_{1(x_i)}^2, N_{1(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{1(x_i)}^n), (N_{2(x_i)}^1, N_{2(x_i)}^2, N_{2(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{2(x_i)}^n) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(T_{N_{2(x_i)}}^1, T_{N_{2(x_i)}}^2, T_{N_{2(x_i)}}^3, \dots, T_{N_{2(x_i)}}^n \right), (N_{3(x_i)}^1, N_{3(x_i)}^2, N_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{3(x_i)}^n) \right) \left(I_{N_{3(x_i)}}^1, I_{N_{3(x_i)}}^2, I_{N_{3(x_i)}}^3, \dots, I_{N_{3(x_i)}}^n \right) \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(N_{4(x_i)}^1, N_{4(x_i)}^2, N_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, N_{4(x_i)}^n \right) \left(F_{N_{4(x_i)}}^1, F_{N_{4(x_i)}}^2, F_{N_{4(x_i)}}^3, \dots, F_{N_{4(x_i)}}^n \right) \right) : N_{1(x_i)}^n, N_{2(x_i)}^n, N_{3(x_i)}^n, N_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \right\}$$

and

$$P^{\check{c}} = \left\{ \left((P_{1(x_i)}^1, P_{1(x_i)}^2, P_{1(x_i)}^3, \dots, P_{1(x_i)}^n), (P_{2(x_i)}^1, P_{2(x_i)}^2, P_{2(x_i)}^3, \dots, P_{2(x_i)}^n) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(T_{P_{2(x_i)}}^1, T_{P_{2(x_i)}}^2, T_{P_{2(x_i)}}^3, \dots, T_{P_{2(x_i)}}^n \right), (P_{3(x_i)}^1, P_{3(x_i)}^2, P_{3(x_i)}^3, \dots, P_{3(x_i)}^n) \right) \left(I_{P_{3(x_i)}}^1, I_{P_{3(x_i)}}^2, I_{P_{3(x_i)}}^3, \dots, I_{P_{3(x_i)}}^n \right) \right. \\ \left. \left. \left(P_{4(x_i)}^1, P_{4(x_i)}^2, P_{4(x_i)}^3, \dots, P_{4(x_i)}^n \right) \left(F_{P_{4(x_i)}}^1, F_{P_{4(x_i)}}^2, F_{P_{4(x_i)}}^3, \dots, F_{P_{4(x_i)}}^n \right) \right) : P_{1(x_i)}^n, P_{2(x_i)}^n, P_{3(x_i)}^n, P_{4(x_i)}^n \in P(E) \right\}.$$

be three MGSVNQSs. Then, the following properties are provided.

- i) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A M^{\check{c}}$
- ii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_O N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_O M^{\check{c}}$
- iii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}'_P N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{U}'_P M^{\check{c}}$
- iv) $M^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A M^{\check{c}}$
- v) $M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O M^{\check{c}}$
- vi) $M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P M^{\check{c}}$
- vii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}}$
- viii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_O (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_O P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_O N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_O P^{\check{c}}$
- ix) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_P (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_P P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_P N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_P P^{\check{c}}$
- x) $M^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{N}_A P^{\check{c}}$
- xi) $M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O (N^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O N^{\check{c}}) \check{O}'_O P^{\check{c}}$
- xii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P (N^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P N^{\check{c}}) \check{O}'_P P^{\check{c}}$
- xiii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_A (M^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A P^{\check{c}})$
- xiv) $M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_A (M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O P^{\check{c}})$
- xv) $M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_P P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_P (M^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_P P^{\check{c}})$
- xvi) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{O}'_O (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}})$
- xvii) $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{O}'_O P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{O}'_O (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}})$

$$\text{xviii) } M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_p (M^{\check{c}} \cap'_p P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_p N^{\check{c}}) \cap'_p (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_p P^{\check{c}})$$

$$\text{xix) } \text{If } M^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \text{ then } M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A N^{\check{c}} = M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_O N^{\check{c}} = M^{\check{c}} \cup'_p N^{\check{c}}$$

$$\text{xx) } \text{If } M^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \text{ then } M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}} = M^{\check{c}} \cap'_O N^{\check{c}} = M^{\check{c}} \cap'_p N^{\check{c}}$$

Proof:

i) From Definition 3.6 for $(M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A N^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i) = (M_1^n(x_i) \cup N_1^n(x_i)), (M, N)^n_2(x_i) = (M_2^n(x_i) \cup N_2^n(x_i)),$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = (M_3^n(x_i) \cup N_3^n(x_i)), (M, N)^n_4(x_i) = (M_4^n(x_i) \cup N_4^n(x_i)).$$

$$T_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}, I_{(M,N)_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}, F_{(M,N)_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p. \tag{1}$$

From Definition 3.6 for $(N^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A M^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$(N, M)^n_1(x_i) = (N_1^n(x_i) \cup M_1^n(x_i)), (N, M)^n_2(x_i) = (N_2^n(x_i) \cup M_2^n(x_i)),$$

$$(N, M)^n_3(x_i) = (N_3^n(x_i) \cup M_3^n(x_i)), (N, M)^n_4(x_i) = (N_4^n(x_i) \cup M_4^n(x_i)).$$

$$T_{(N,M)_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}, I_{(N,M)_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}, F_{(N,M)_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p. \tag{2}$$

and from Definition 3.5, (1) and (2), we get

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A N^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A M^{\check{c}}$$

Proof of {ii, iii} are obtained similar to i.

iv) From Definition 3.6 and ii, for $(M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i) = (M_1^n(x_i) \cap N_1^n(x_i)), (M, N)^n_2(x_i) = (M_2^n(x_i) \cap N_2^n(x_i)),$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = (M_3^n(x_i) \cap N_3^n(x_i)), (M, N)^n_4(x_i) = (M_4^n(x_i) \cap N_4^n(x_i)).$$

$$T_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}, I_{(M,N)_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}, F_{(M,N)_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j, n=1, \dots, p. \tag{3}$$

From Definition 3.6 and ii, for $(N^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A M^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$(N, M)^n_1(x_i) = (N_1^n(x_i) \cap M_1^n(x_i)), (N, M)^n_2(x_i) = (N_2^n(x_i) \cap M_2^n(x_i)),$$

$$(N, M)^n_3(x_i) = (N_3^n(x_i) \cap M_3^n(x_i)), (N, M)^n_4(x_i) = (N_4^n(x_i) \cap M_4^n(x_i)).$$

$$T_{(N,M)_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}, I_{(N,M)_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}, F_{(N,M)_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$ (4)

and from Definition 3.5, (3) and (4), we get

Proof of {v, vi} are obtained similar to iv.

vii) We assume that

$$T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) = T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i), I_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) = I_{(P)_2}^n(x_i), F_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) = F_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)$$

For Definition 3.6 $M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$(M, (N, P))_1^n(x_i) = (M_1^n(x_i) \cup (N_1^n(x_i) \cup P_1^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))_2^n(x_i) = (M_2^n(x_i) \cup (N_2^n(x_i) \cup P_2^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))_3^n(x_i) = (M_3^n(x_i) \cup (N_3^n(x_i) \cup P_3^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))_4^n(x_i) = (M_4^n(x_i) \cup (N_4^n(x_i) \cup P_4^n(x_i))).$$

$$T_{(M,(N,P))_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + \frac{T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}, I_{(M,(N,P))_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + \frac{I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(P)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2},$$

$$F_{(M,(N,P))_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + \frac{F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(P)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$ (5)

For Definition 3.6, i. for $(M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}$

$$((M, N), P)_1^n(x_i) = ((M_1^n(x_i) \cup N_1^n(x_i)) \cup P_1^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N), P)_2^n(x_i) = ((M_2^n(x_i) \cup N_2^n(x_i)) \cup P_2^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N), P)_3^n(x_i) = ((M_3^n(x_i) \cup N_3^n(x_i)) \cup P_3^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N), P)_4^n(x_i) = ((M_4^n(x_i) \cup N_4^n(x_i)) \cup P_4^n(x_i)).$$

$$T_{((M,N),P)_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{\frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)}{2} + T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}, I_{((M,N),P)_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{\frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)}{2} + I_{(P)_3}^n(x_i)}{2},$$

$$F_{((M,N),P)_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{\frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)}{2} + F_{(P)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}$$

$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.$ (6)

From Definition 3.5, (5) and (6) we get

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{\cup}_A P^{\check{c}}$$

Proof of {viii, ix} are obtained similar to vii.

x) We assume that

$$T_{(M)_2(x_i)}^n = T_{(P)_2(x_i)}^n, \quad I_{(M)_2(x_i)}^n = I_{(P)_2(x_i)}^n, \quad F_{(M)_2(x_i)}^n = F_{(P)_2(x_i)}^n$$

From Definition 3.6 for $M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}}$, we get

$$(M, (N, P))_1^n(x_i) = (M_1^n(x_i) \cap (N_1^n(x_i) \cap P_1^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))_2^n(x_i) = (M_2^n(x_i) \cap (N_2^n(x_i) \cap P_2^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))_3^n(x_i) = (M_3^n(x_i) \cap (N_3^n(x_i) \cap P_3^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))_4^n(x_i) = (M_4^n(x_i) \cap (N_4^n(x_i) \cap P_4^n(x_i))).$$

$$T_{(M,(N,P))_2(x_i)}^n = \frac{T_{(M)_2(x_i)}^n + \frac{T_{(N)_2(x_i)}^n + T_{(P)_2(x_i)}^n}{2}}{2}, \quad I_{(M,(N,P))_3(x_i)}^n = \frac{I_{(M)_3(x_i)}^n + \frac{I_{(N)_3(x_i)}^n + I_{(P)_3(x_i)}^n}{2}}{2},$$

$$F_{(M,(N,P))_4(x_i)}^n = \frac{F_{(M)_4(x_i)}^n + \frac{F_{(N)_4(x_i)}^n + F_{(P)_4(x_i)}^n}{2}}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p. \tag{7}$$

For Definition 3.6 for $(M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}}$

$$((M, N), P)_1^n(x_i) = ((M_1^n(x_i) \cap N_1^n(x_i)) \cap P_1^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N), P)_2^n(x_i) = ((M_2^n(x_i) \cap N_2^n(x_i)) \cap P_2^n(x_i))$$

$$((M, N), P)_3^n(x_i) = ((M_3^n(x_i) \cap N_3^n(x_i)) \cap P_3^n(x_i)),$$

$$((M, N), P)_4^n(x_i) = ((M_4^n(x_i) \cap N_4^n(x_i)) \cap P_4^n(x_i)).$$

$$T_{((M,N),P)_2(x_i)}^n = \frac{\frac{T_{(M)_2(x_i)}^n + T_{(N)_2(x_i)}^n}{2} + T_{(P)_2(x_i)}^n}{2}, \quad I_{((M,N),P)_3(x_i)}^n = \frac{\frac{I_{(M)_3(x_i)}^n + I_{(N)_3(x_i)}^n}{2} + I_{(P)_3(x_i)}^n}{2},$$

$$F_{((M,N),P)_4(x_i)}^n = \frac{\frac{F_{(M)_4(x_i)}^n + F_{(N)_4(x_i)}^n}{2} + F_{(P)_4(x_i)}^n}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p. \tag{8}$$

From Definition 3.5, (7) and (8) we get

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}}$$

Proof of {xi, xii} are obtained similar to x.

xiii) From Definition 3.6 for $M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A P^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$(M, (N, P))^n_1(x_i) = (M_1^n(x_i) \cap (N_1^n(x_i) \cup P_1^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))^n_2(x_i) = (M_2^n(x_i) \cap (N_2^n(x_i) \cup P_2^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))^n_3(x_i) = (M_3^n(x_i) \cap (N_3^n(x_i) \cup P_3^n(x_i))),$$

$$(M, (N, P))^n_4(x_i) = (M_4^n(x_i) \cap (N_4^n(x_i) \cup P_4^n(x_i))).$$

$$T_{(M,(N,P))_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + \frac{T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}, \quad I_{(M,(N,P))_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + \frac{I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(P)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2},$$

$$F_{(M,(N,P))_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + \frac{F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(P)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p. \tag{9}$$

For Definition 3.6, $(M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{\cup}_A (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$((M, N), (M, P))^n_1(x_i) = ((M_1^n(x_i) \cap N_1^n(x_i)) \cup (M_1^n(x_i) \cap P_1^n(x_i))),$$

$$((M, N), (M, P))^n_2(x_i) = ((M_2^n(x_i) \cap N_2^n(x_i)) \cup (M_2^n(x_i) \cap P_2^n(x_i))),$$

$$((M, N), (M, P))^n_3(x_i) = ((M_3^n(x_i) \cap N_3^n(x_i)) \cup (M_3^n(x_i) \cap P_3^n(x_i))),$$

$$((M, N), (M, P))^n_4(x_i) = ((M_4^n(x_i) \cap N_4^n(x_i)) \cup (M_4^n(x_i) \cap P_4^n(x_i))),$$

$$T_{((M,N),(M,P))_2}^n(x_i) = \frac{\frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)}{2} + \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2},$$

$$I_{((M,N),(M,P))_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{\frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)}{2} + \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(P)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2},$$

$$F_{((M,N),(M,P))_4}^n(x_i) = \frac{\frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)}{2} + \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(P)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}$$

$$i=1, \dots, j, n=1, \dots, p. \tag{10}$$

From Definition 3.5, (9) and (10) we get

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A N^{\check{c}}) \check{\cup}_A (M^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}})$$

Proof of {xiv, xv} are obtained similar to xiii.

xvi) From Definition 3.6 for $M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{\cap}_A P^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 (M, (N, P))_1^n(x_i) &= \left(M_1^n(x_i) \cup (N_1^n(x_i) \cap P_1^n(x_i)) \right), \\
 (M, (N, P))_2^n(x_i) &= \left(M_2^n(x_i) \cup (N_2^n(x_i) \cap P_2^n(x_i)) \right) \\
 (M, (N, P))_3^n(x_i) &= \left(M_3^n(x_i) \cup (N_3^n(x_i) \cap P_3^n(x_i)) \right), \\
 (M, (N, P))_4^n(x_i) &= \left(M_4^n(x_i) \cup (N_4^n(x_i) \cap P_4^n(x_i)) \right) \\
 T_{(M,(N,P))_2}^n(x_i) &= \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + \frac{T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}, \quad I_{(M,(N,P))_3}^n(x_i) = \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + \frac{I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(P)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}, \\
 F_{(M,(N,P))_4}^n(x_i) &= \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + \frac{F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(P)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2} \\
 i=1, \dots, j; n=1, \dots, p.
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

For Definition 3.6, $(M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}) \cap'_o (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}})$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 ((M, N), (M, P))_1^n(x_i) &= \left((M_1^n(x_i) \cup N_1^n(x_i)) \cap (M_1^n(x_i) \cup P_1^n(x_i)) \right), \\
 ((M, N), (M, P))_2^n(x_i) &= \left((M_2^n(x_i) \cup N_2^n(x_i)) \cap (M_2^n(x_i) \cup P_2^n(x_i)) \right), \\
 ((M, N), (M, P))_3^n(x_i) &= \left((M_3^n(x_i) \cup N_3^n(x_i)) \cap (M_3^n(x_i) \cup P_3^n(x_i)) \right), \\
 ((M, N), (M, P))_4^n(x_i) &= \left((M_4^n(x_i) \cup N_4^n(x_i)) \cap (M_4^n(x_i) \cup P_4^n(x_i)) \right), \\
 T_{((M,N),(M,P))_2}^n(x_i) &= \frac{\frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)}{2} + \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(P)_2}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}, \\
 I_{((M,N),(M,P))_3}^n(x_i) &= \frac{\frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)}{2} + \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(P)_3}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2}, \\
 F_{((M,N),(M,P))_4}^n(x_i) &= \frac{\frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)}{2} + \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(P)_4}^n(x_i)}{2}}{2} \\
 i=1, \dots, j, n=1, \dots, p.
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

From Definition 3.5, (11) and (12) we get

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A (N^{\check{c}} \check{N}_A P^{\check{c}}) = (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A N^{\check{c}}) \cap'_o (M^{\check{c}} \check{U}_A P^{\check{c}})$$

Proof of {xvii, xviii} are obtained similar to xvi.

xi) We assume that $M^{\check{c}} = N^{\check{c}}$. From Definition 3.5 and Definition 3.6, we obtain

$$T_{(M,N)_2}^n(x_i) = \min\{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i), T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)\} = \frac{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i) + T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)}{2} = \max\{T_{(M)_2}^n(x_i), T_{(N)_2}^n(x_i)\}$$

$$I_{(M,N)_3}^n(x_i) = \max\{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i), I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)\} = \frac{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i) + I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)}{2} = \min\{I_{(M)_3}^n(x_i), I_{(N)_3}^n(x_i)\}$$

$$F_{(M,N)_4}^n(x_i) = \max\{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i), F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)\} = \frac{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i) + F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)}{2} = \min\{F_{(M)_4}^n(x_i), F_{(N)_4}^n(x_i)\} \tag{13}$$

Also,

$$(M, N)^n_1(x_i) = M_1^n(x_i) \cup N_1^n(x_i), (M, N)^n_2(x_i) = M_2^n(x_i) \cup N_2^n(x_i)$$

$$(M, N)^n_3(x_i) = M_3^n(x_i) \cup N_3^n(x_i), (M, N)^n_4(x_i) = M_4^n(x_i) \cup N_4^n(x_i) \tag{14}$$

Thus from (13) and (14) we get

$$M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_A N^{\check{c}} = M^{\check{c}} \check{\cup}_O N^{\check{c}} = M^{\check{c}} \cup'_p N^{\check{c}}$$

Proof of xx are obtained similar to xix.

Example 3.8: Let

$$\check{C}_{n_1} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{M, G\}, \{R, L\}, \{M\}, \{E, Ge\}), (\{R, L\}, \{C\}, \{G\}, \{C, L\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.4), \\ (\{E, Ge\}, \{M, G\}, \{C, R\}, \{B\})(0.5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4), (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.1, 0.3, 0.3, 0.3), \\ (\{E\}, \{E, M\}, \{R, G\}, \{B, M, G\}), (\{C, L\}, \{Ge, G\}, \{E\}, \{L\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.1), \\ (\{M, G\}, \{R\}, \{C\}, \{C\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.7), (\{R, B\}, \{L, C\}, \{L, Ge, M\}, \{Ge, E, C\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2), \\ (\{B, Ge, E\}, \{Ge, E\}, \{L, C, B\}, \{Ge\}), (\{L\}, \{L, M\}, \{M, G\}, \{G, C, B\})(0.3, 0.5, 0.5, 0.8), \\ (\{G, R\}, \{G, R\}, \{R\}, \{E, M\})(0.5, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), (\{M\}, \{B\}, \{E\}, \{R\})(0.2, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1), \\ (\{G, M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, C\}, \{M, C, G\}), (\{L, B\}, \{Ge, C, B\}, \{M, G\}, \{L\})(0.3, 0.7, 0.5, 0.2), \\ (\{R, E\}, \{R\}, \{R\}, \{Ge, R\})(0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5), (\{Ge\}, \{E\}, \{B\}, \{B\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.3), \\ (\{G, E\}, \{C\}, \{E\}, \{G\}), (\{Ge, M\}, \{M\}, \{L, G\}, \{E, M\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.3, 0.5), \\ (\{C, R\}, \{B, L\}, \{C, R\}, \{C, R\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.3), (\{L, B\}, \{R, E\}, \{Ge, M, B\}, \{L, B\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.6, 0.2) \end{array} \right\}$$

and

$$\check{C}_{n_2} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (\{G, E\}, \{R, K\}, \{E\}, \{M\}), (\{M, L\}, \{E, Ge\}, \{G\}, \{G, C\})(0.6, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3), \\ (\{M\}, \{Ge, G\}, \{C, R\}, \{E\})(0.4, 0.5, 0.1, 0.4), (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6), \\ (\{Ge, E\}, \{G, M\}, \{L\}, \{G, B\}), (\{E, L\}, \{M\}, \{G, Ge, E\}, \{R\})(0.5, 0.3, 0.4, 0.1), \\ (\{C, G\}, \{E, R\}, \{M, Ge\}, \{L\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.5), (\{R, E\}, \{M\}, \{L, C\}, \{E, K, G\})(0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.2), \\ (\{G, E\}, \{B, Ge, E\}, \{C, B\}, \{D\}), (\{E, Ge\}, \{L, G, M\}, \{R\}, \{C, B\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.5), \\ (\{E, M\}, \{C, Ge, G\}, \{B\}, \{L\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5), (\{Ge, E\}, \{B, G\}, \{M, L\}, \{R\})(0.5, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2), \\ (\{M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, R\}, \{B, L\}), (\{E, B, Ge\}, \{C\}, \{M\}, \{G, L\})(0.4, 0.1, 0.3, 0.6), \\ (\{B, R, E\}, \{L\}, \{Ge\}, \{M\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6), (\{B, Ge\}, \{E, G\}, \{M, L\}, \{R\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.1), \\ (\{G, E, Ge\}, \{C\}, \{R, M\}, \{B\}), (\{Ge, E, M\}, \{G\}, \{L\}, \{E, B, R\})(0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), \\ (\{E, R\}, \{B, Ge, L\}, \{C, G\}, \{R\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4), (\{G\}, \{E, B\}, \{Ge, M\}, \{L, R\})(0.4, 0.4, 0.2, 0.3) \end{array} \right\}$$

be two MGSVNQSs such that in Example 3.4, the questions solved by a student from different textbooks for four consecutive weeks in two different months be represented by the MGSVNQSs.

i) For $\check{C}_{n_1}$ ve $\check{C}_{n_2}$, the 'Average $\cup$ ' operation is defined as follows;

$$\begin{aligned}
 \check{c}_{n_1} \check{U}_A \check{c}_{n_2} = & \left\{ \left(\begin{array}{l} \{M, G, E\} = \{M, G\} \cup \{G, E\}, \\ \{R, L, C\} = \{R, L\} \cup \{R, C\}, \\ \{M, E\} = \{M\} \cup \{E\}, \\ \{E, G, M\} = \{E, G\} \cup \{M\} \end{array} \right), \left(\begin{array}{l} \{R, L, M\} = \{R, L\} \cup \{M, L\}, \\ \{C, E, Ge\} = \{C\} \cup \{E, Ge\}, \\ \{G\} = \{G\} \cup \{G\}, \\ \{C, L, G\} = \{C, L\} \cup \{G, C\} \end{array} \right) T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2(x_1)}^1, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{E, Ge, M\} = \{E, Ge\} \cup \{M\}, \\ \{M, G, Ge\} = \{M, G\} \cup \{Ge, G\}, \\ \{C, R\} = \{C, R\} \cup \{C, R\}, \\ \{B, E\} = \{B\} \cup \{E\} \end{array} \right) I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2(x_1)}^1, \left(\begin{array}{l} \{B\} = \{B\} \cup \{B\}, \\ \{Ge, B\} = \{Ge, B\} \cup \{Ge, B\}, \\ \{L, Ge\} = \{L, Ge\} \cup \{L, Ge\}, \\ \{M, Ge\} = \{M, Ge\} \cup \{M, Ge\} \end{array} \right) F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2(x_1)}^1, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{E, Ge\} = \{E\} \cup \{Ge, E\}, \\ \{E, M, G\} = \{E, M\} \cup \{G, M\}, \\ \{R, G, L\} = \{R, G\} \cup \{L\}, \\ \{B, M, G\} = \{B, M, G\} \cup \{G, B\} \end{array} \right), \left(\begin{array}{l} \{C, L, E\} = \{C, L\} \cup \{E, L\}, \\ \{Ge, G, M\} = \{Ge, G\} \cup \{M\}, \\ \{E, G, Ge\} = \{E\} \cup \{G, Ge, E\}, \\ \{L, R\} = \{L\} \cup \{R\} \end{array} \right) T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3(x_2)}^2, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{M, G, C\} = \{M, G\} \cup \{C, G\}, \\ \{R, E\} = \{R\} \cup \{E, R\}, \\ \{C, M, Ge\} = \{C\} \cup \{M, Ge\}, \\ \{C\} = \{L\} \cup \{C, L\} \end{array} \right) I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3(x_2)}^2, \left(\begin{array}{l} \{R, B, E\} = \{R, B\} \cup \{R, E\}, \\ \{L, C, M\} = \{L, C\} \cup \{M\}, \\ \{L, Ge, M, C\} = \{L, Ge, M\} \cup \{L, C\}, \\ \{Ge, E, C, G\} = \{Ge, E, C\} \cup \{E, C, G\} \end{array} \right) F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3(x_2)}^2, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{B, E, Ge, G\} = \{B, Ge, E\} \cup \{G, E\}, \\ \{Ge, E, B\} = \{Ge, E\} \cup \{B, Ge, E\}, \\ \{L, C, B\} = \{L, C, B\} \cup \{C, B\}, \\ \{Ge, R\} = \{Ge\} \cup \{R\} \end{array} \right), \left(\begin{array}{l} \{L, E, Ge\} = \{L\} \cup \{E, Ge\}, \\ \{L, M, G\} = \{L, M\} \cup \{L, G, M\}, \\ \{M, G, R\} = \{M, G\} \cup \{R\}, \\ \{G, C, B\} = \{G, C, B\} \cup \{C, B\} \end{array} \right) T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4(x_3)}^3, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{G, R, E, M\} = \{G, R\} \cup \{E, M\}, \\ \{G, R, C, Ge\} = \{G, R\} \cup \{C, Ge, G\}, \\ \{R, B\} = \{R\} \cup \{B\}, \\ \{E, M, L\} = \{E, M\} \cup \{L\} \end{array} \right) I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4(x_3)}^3, \left(\begin{array}{l} \{M, Ge, E\} = \{M\} \cup \{Ge, E\}, \\ \{B, G\} = \{B\} \cup \{B, G\}, \\ \{E, M, L\} = \{E\} \cup \{M, L\}, \\ \{R\} = \{R\} \cup \{R\} \end{array} \right) F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4(x_3)}^3, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{G, M\} = \{G, M\} \cup \{M\}, \\ \{C\} = \{C\} \cup \{C\}, \\ \{Ge, E, C, R\} = \{Ge, E, C\} \cup \{Ge, E, R\}, \\ \{M, C, G, B, L\} = \{M, C, G\} \cup \{B, L\} \end{array} \right), \left(\begin{array}{l} \{L, B, E, Ge\} = \{L, B\} \cup \{E, B, Ge\}, \\ \{Ge, C, B\} = \{Ge, C, B\} \cup \{C\}, \\ \{M, G\} = \{M, G\} \cup \{M\}, \\ \{L, G\} = \{L\} \cup \{L, G\} \end{array} \right) T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5(x_4)}^4, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{R, E, B\} = \{R, E\} \cup \{B, R, E\}, \\ \{R, L\} = \{R\} \cup \{L\}, \\ \{R, Ge\} = \{R\} \cup \{Ge\}, \\ \{Ge, R, M\} = \{Ge, R\} \cup \{M\} \end{array} \right) I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5(x_4)}^4, \left(\begin{array}{l} \{Ge, B\} = \{Ge\} \cup \{B, Ge\}, \\ \{E, G\} = \{E\} \cup \{E, G\}, \\ \{B, M, L\} = \{B\} \cup \{M, L\}, \\ \{B, R\} = \{B\} \cup \{R\} \end{array} \right) F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5(x_4)}^4, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{G, E, Ge\} = \{G, E\} \cup \{G, E, Ge\}, \\ \{C\} = \{C\} \cup \{C\}, \\ \{E, R, M\} = \{E\} \cup \{R, M\}, \\ \{G, B\} = \{G\} \cup \{B\} \end{array} \right), \left(\begin{array}{l} \{Ge, M, E\} = \{Ge, M\} \cup \{Ge, E, M\}, \\ \{M, G\} = \{M\} \cup \{G\}, \\ \{L, G\} = \{L, G\} \cup \{L\}, \\ \{E, M, B, R\} = \{E, M\} \cup \{E, B, R\} \end{array} \right) T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6(x_5)}^5, \\
 & \left(\begin{array}{l} \{C, R, E\} = \{C, R\} \cup \{E, R\}, \\ \{B, L, Ge\} = \{B, L\} \cup \{B, Ge, L\}, \\ \{C, R, G\} = \{C, R\} \cup \{R, G\}, \\ \{C, R\} = \{C, R\} \cup \{R\} \end{array} \right) I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6(x_5)}^5, \left(\begin{array}{l} \{L, B, G\} = \{L, B\} \cup \{G\}, \\ \{R, E, B\} = \{R, E\} \cup \{E, B\}, \\ \{Ge, M, B\} = \{Ge, M, B\} \cup \{Ge, M\}, \\ \{L, B, R\} = \{L, B\} \cup \{L, R\} \end{array} \right) F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6(x_5)}^5, \end{aligned}$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_1) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_2}(x_1) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.6)}{2} = 0.45,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_2) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_2}(x_2) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.2)}{2} = 0.2,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_3) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_2}(x_3) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.1)}{2} = 0.1,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_4) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_2}(x_4) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_2}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.4+0.3)}{2} = 0.35$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_1) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_1) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.4)}{2} = 0.45,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_2) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_2) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.5)}{2} = 0.5,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_3) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_3) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.1)}{2} = 0.2,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_4) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_4) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.4+0.4)}{2} = 0.4$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_1) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.2)}{2} = 0.15,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_2) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.5)}{2} = 0.4,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_3) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.3)}{2} = 0.3,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_4) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.6)}{2} = 0.45$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_1) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_1) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.5)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_2) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_2) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.4+0.3)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_3) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_3) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_4) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_4) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.1)}{2} = 0.1$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_1) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_1) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.6+0.3)}{2} = 0.45,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_2) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_2) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.2)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_3) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}^2(x_3) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}^2(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.1)}{2} = 0.1,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_4) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_4) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.7+0.5)}{2} = 0.6$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_1) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_1) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.5)}{2} = 0.4,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_2) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_2) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_3) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_3) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.6+0.3)}{2} = 0.45,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_4) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_3}(x_4) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_3}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.2)}{2} = 0.2$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_1) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.2)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_2) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.5)}{2} = 0.5,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_3) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.6)}{2} = 0.55,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_4) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.8+0.5)}{2} = 0.65$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_1) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.2)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_2) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_3) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.3)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_4) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.5)}{2} = 0.3$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_1) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.2)}{2} = 0.2,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_2) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.1)}{2} = 0.15,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_3) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.3)}{2} = 0.3,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_4}(x_4) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_4}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.2)}{2} = 0.15$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_1) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_1) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_2) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_2) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.7+0.1)}{2} = 0.4,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_3) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_3) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.3)}{2} = 0.4,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_4) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_4) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.6)}{2} = 0.4$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_1) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_1) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.4+0.2)}{2} = 0.3,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_2) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_2) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.4)}{2} = 0.3,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_3) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_3) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.3)}{2} = 0.3,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_4) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_4) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.6)}{2} = 0.55$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_1) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_1) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.2)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_2) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_2) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.4)}{2} = 0.25$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_3) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_3) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.6)}{2} = 0.45,$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_4) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_5}(x_4) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_5}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.1)}{2} = 0.2$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_1) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_1) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.6+0.4)}{2} = 0.5,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_2) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_2) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.3)}{2} = 0.3,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_3) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_3) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.2)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$T_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_4) = \frac{T_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_4) + T_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.5+0.1)}{2} = 0.3$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_1) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_1) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.3)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_2) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_2) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_2)}{2} = \frac{(0.4+0.1)}{2} = 0.25,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_3) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_3) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_3)}{2} = \frac{(0.1+0.2)}{2} = 0.15,$$

$$I_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_4) = \frac{I_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_4) + I_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_4)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35$$

$$F_{(\check{c}_{n_1}, \check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_1) = \frac{F_{(\check{c}_{n_1})_6}(x_1) + F_{(\check{c}_{n_2})_6}(x_1)}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_1}, \check{C}_{n_2})_6(x_2)} = \frac{F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_1})_6(x_2)} + F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_2})_6(x_2)}}{2} = \frac{(0.3+0.4)}{2} = 0.35,$$

$$F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_1}, \check{C}_{n_2})_6(x_3)} = \frac{F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_1})_6(x_3)} + F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_2})_6(x_3)}}{2} = \frac{(0.6+0.2)}{2} = 0.4,$$

$$F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_1}, \check{C}_{n_2})_6(x_4)} = \frac{F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_1})_6(x_4)} + F^5_{(\check{C}_{n_2})_6(x_4)}}{2} = \frac{(0.2+0.3)}{2} = 0.25$$

Thus we obtain the set $\check{C}_{n_1} \check{U}_A \check{C}_{n_2}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \check{C}_{n_1} \check{U}_A \check{C}_{n_2} = & \{ \{ \{ M, G, E \}, \{ R, L, C \}, \{ M, E \}, \{ E, G, M \} \}, \\ & (\{ R, L, M \}, \{ K, E, Ge \}, \{ G \} \{ C, L, G \}) (0.45, 0.2, 0.1, 0.35), \\ & (\{ E, Ge, M \}, \{ M, G, Ge \}, \{ C, R \}, \{ B, E \}) (0.45, 0.5, 0.2, 0.4), \\ & (\{ B \}, \{ Ge, B \}, \{ L, Ge \}, \{ M, Ge \}) (0.15, 0.4, 0.3, 0.45) \}, \\ & \{ (\{ E, Ge \}, \{ E, M, G \}, \{ R, G, L \}, \{ B, M, G \}), \\ & (\{ C, L, E \}, \{ Ge, G, M \}, \{ E, G, Ge \}, \{ L, R \}) (0.35, 0.35, 0.35, 0.1), \\ & (\{ M, G, C \}, \{ R, E \}, \{ C, M, Ge \}, \{ C, L \}) (0.45, 0.25, 0.1, 0.6), \\ & (\{ R, B, E \}, \{ L, C, M \}, \{ L, Ge, M, C \}, \{ Ge, E, C, G \}) (0.4, 0.35, 0.45, 0.2) \}, \\ & \{ (\{ B, Ge, E, G \}, \{ Ge, E, B \}, \{ L, C, B \}, \{ Ge, R \}), \\ & (\{ L, E, Ge \}, \{ L, M, G \}, \{ M, G, R \} \{ G, C, B \}) (0.25, 0.5, 0.55, 0.65), \\ & (\{ G, R, E, M \}, \{ G, R, C, Ge, G \}, \{ R, B \}, \{ E, M, L \}) (0.35, 0.35, 0.35, 0.3), \\ & (\{ M, Ge, E \}, \{ B, G \}, \{ E, M, L \}, \{ R \}) (0.2, 0.15, 0.3, 0.15), \\ & \{ (\{ G, M \}, \{ C, M \}, \{ Ge, E, C, R \}, \{ M, C, G, B, L \}), \\ & (\{ L, B, E, Ge \}, \{ Ge, C, B \}, \{ M, G \} \{ L, G \}) (0.35, 0.4, 0.4, 0.4), \\ & (\{ R, E, B \}, \{ R, E \}, \{ R, Ge \}, \{ Ge, R, M \}) (0.3, 0.3, 0.3, 0.55), \\ & (\{ Ge, B \}, \{ E, G \}, \{ B, M, L \}, \{ B, R \}) (0.25, 0.25, 0.45, 0.2) \}, \\ & \{ (\{ G, E, Ge \}, \{ C \}, \{ E, R, M \}, \{ G, B \}), \\ & (\{ Ge, M, E \}, \{ M, G \}, \{ L, G \} \{ E, M, B, R \}) (0.5, 0.3, 0.25, 0.3), \\ & (\{ C, R, E \}, \{ B, L, Ge \}, \{ C, R, G \}, \{ C, R \}) (0.25, 0.25, 0.15, 0.35), \\ & (\{ L, B, G \}, \{ R, E, B \}, \{ Ge, M, B \}, \{ L, B, R \}) (0.35, 0.35, 0.4, 0.25) \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

ii) The 'Average $\cap$ ' operator for $\check{C}_{n_1}$ ve $\check{C}_{n_2}$ is obtained from Definition 3.6 and similar to i such that

$$\begin{aligned} \check{C}_{n_1} \check{\cap}_A \check{C}_{n_2} = & \{(\{G\}, \{R\}, \{\emptyset\}, \{\emptyset\}), (\{L\}, \emptyset, \{G\}\{C\})(0.45,0.2,0.1,0.35), \\ & (\emptyset, \{G\}, \{C, R\}, \emptyset)(0.45,0.5,0.2,0.4), (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.15,0.4,0.3,0.45)\}, \\ & \{(\{E\}, \{M\}, \emptyset, \{B, G\}), (\{L\}, \emptyset, \{E\}, \emptyset)(0.35,0.35,0.35,0.1), (\{G\}, \emptyset, \{C\}, \emptyset)(0.45,0.25,0.1,0.6), \\ & (\{R\}, \emptyset, \{L\}, \{E, C\})(0.4,0.35,0.45,0.2)\}, \\ & \{(\{E\}, \{Ge, E\}, \{C, B\}, \emptyset), (\emptyset, \{L, M\}, \{\emptyset\}\{C, B\})(0.25,0.5,0.55,0.65), \\ & (\emptyset, \{G\}, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.35,0.35,0.35,0.3), (\emptyset, \{B\}, \emptyset, \{R\})(0.2,0.15,0.3,0.15)\}, \\ & \{(\{M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, C\}, \emptyset), (\{B\}, \{C\}, \{M\}, \{L\}) (0.35,0.4,0.4,0.4), \\ & (\{R, E\}, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.3,0.3,0.3,0.55), (\{Ge\}, \{E\}, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.25,0.25,0.45,0.2)\}, \\ & \{(\{G, E\}, \{C\}, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{Ge, M\}, \emptyset, \{L, G\}\{E\})(0.5,0.3,0.25,0.3), \\ & (\{R\}, \{B\}, \{C\}, \{R\})(0.25,0.25,0.15,0.35), (\emptyset, \{E\}, \{Ge, M\}, \{L\})(0.35,0.35,0.4,0.25)\}. \end{aligned}$$

iii) For $\check{C}_{n_1}$ ve $\check{C}_{n_2}$, the operation "optimistic $\cup$ " is obtained from Definition 3.6 and similar to i such that

$$\begin{aligned} \check{C}_{n_1} \check{\cup}_O \check{C}_{n_2} = & \{(\{M, G, E\}, \{R, L, C\}, \{M, E\}, \{M, E, G\}), \\ & (\{R, L, M\}, \{C, E, Ge\}, \{G\}, \{C, L, G\})(0.6,0.2,0.1,0.4), \\ & (\{E, Ge, M\}, \{M, G, Ge\}, \{C, R\}, \{B, E\})(0.4,0.5,0.1,0.4), \\ & (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.1,0.3,0.3,0.3)\}, \\ & \{(\{E, Ge\}, \{E, M, G\}, \{R, G, L\}, \{B, M, G\}), \\ & (\{C, L, E\}, \{Ge, G, M\}, \{E, G, Ge\}\{L, R\})(0.5,0.4,0.4,0.1), \\ & (\{M, G, C\}, \{R, E\}, \{C, M, Ge\}, \{C, L\})(0.3,0.2,0.1,0.5), \\ & (\{R, B, E\}, \{L, C, M\}, \{L, Ge, M, C\}, \{Ge, E, C, G\})(0.3,0.3,0.3,0.2)\}, \\ & \{(\{B, Ge, E, G\}, \{Ge, E, B\}, \{L, C, B\}, \{Ge, R\}), \\ & (\{L, E, Ge\}, \{L, M, G\}, \{M, G, R\}, \{G, C, B\})(0.3,0.5,0.6,0.8), \\ & (\{G, R, E, M\}, \{G, R, C, Ge\}, \{R, B\}, \{E, M, L\})(0.2,0.3,0.2,0.1), \\ & (\{M, Ge, E\}, \{B, G\}, \{E, M, L\}, \{R\})(0.2,0.1,0.3,0.1)\}, \\ & \{(\{G, M\}, \{C, M\}, \{Ge, E, C, R\}, \{M, C, G, B, L\}), \\ & (\{L, B, E, Ge\}, \{Ge, C, B\}, \{M, G\}, \{L, G\})(0.4,0.7,0.5,0.6), \\ & (\{R, E, B\}, \{R, L\}, \{R, Ge\}, \{Ge, R, M\})(0.2,0.2,0.3,0.5), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\{Ge, B\}, \{E, G\}, \{B, M, L\}, \{B, R\})(0.2, 0.1, 0.3, 0.1), \\ & (\{G, E, Ge\}, \{C\}, \{E, R, M\}, \{G, B\}), \\ & (\{Ge, M, E\}, \{M, G\}, \{L, G\}, \{E, M, B, R\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.3, 0.5), \\ & (\{C, R, E\}, \{B, L, Ge\}, \{C, R, G\}, \{C, R\})(0.2, 0.1, 0.1, 0.3), \\ & (\{L, B, G\}, \{R, E, B\}, \{Ge, M, B\}, \{L, B, R\})(0.3, 0.3, 0.2, 0.2)}. \end{aligned}$$

iv) The 'Optimistic $\cap$ ' operation for $\check{C}_{n_1}$ ve $\check{C}_{n_2}$ is obtained from Definition 3.6 and similar to i such that

$$\begin{aligned} \check{C}_{n_1} \check{\cap}_o \check{C}_{n_2} = & \{(\{G\}, \{R\}, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{L\}, \emptyset, \{G\}, \{C\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3), \\ & (\emptyset, \{G\}, \{C, R\}, \emptyset)(0.5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4), \\ & (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6)\}, \\ & (\{E\}, \{M\}, \emptyset, \{B, G\}), (\{L\}, \emptyset, \{E\}, \emptyset)(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.1), \\ & (\{G\}, \emptyset, \{C\}, \emptyset)(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.7), \\ & (\{R\}, \emptyset, \{L\}, \{E, C\})(0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.2)\}, \\ & (\{E\}, \{Ge, E\}, \{C, B\}, \emptyset), (\emptyset, \{L, M\}, \emptyset, \{C, B\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.5), (\emptyset, \{G\}, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5), \\ & (\emptyset, \{B\}, \emptyset, \{R\})(0.5, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)\}, \\ & (\{M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, C\}, \emptyset), (\{B\}, \{C\}, \{M\}, \{L\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2), (\{R, E\}, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.4, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6), \\ & (\{Ge\}, \{E\}, \emptyset, \emptyset) (0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3)\}, \\ & (\{G, E\}, \{C\}, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{Ge, M\}, \emptyset, \{L, G\}, \{E\})(0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), \\ & (\{R\}, \{B\}, \{C\}, \{R\})(0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.4), (\emptyset, \{E\}, \{Ge, M\}, \{L\})(0.4, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3)\}. \end{aligned}$$

v) The 'Pessimistic $\cup$ ' operation for $\check{C}_{n_1}$ and $\check{C}_{n_2}$ is obtained from Definition 3.6 and similar to i such that

$$\begin{aligned} \check{C}_{n_1} \check{\cup}_p \check{C}_{n_2} = & \{(\{M, G, E\}, \{R, L, C\}, \{M, E\}, \{M, E, G\}), \\ & (\{R, L, M\}, \{C, E, Ge\}, \{G\}, \{C, L, G\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3), \\ & (\{E, Ge, M\}, \{M, G, Ge\}, \{C, R\}, \{B, E\})(0.5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4), \\ & (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6)\}, \\ & (\{E, Ge\}, \{E, M, G\}, \{R, G, L\}, \{B, M, G\}), \\ & (\{C, L, E\}, \{Ge, G, M\}, \{E, G, Ge\}, \{L, R\})(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.1), \\ & (\{M, G, C\}, \{R, E\}, \{C, M, Ge\}, \{C, L\})(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.7), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& (\{R, B, E\}, \{L, C, M\}, \{L, Ge, M, C\}, \{Ge, E, C, G\})(0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.2), \\
& (\{B, Ge, E, G\}, \{Ge, E, B\}, \{L, C, B\}, \{Ge, R\}), \\
& (\{L, E, Ge\}, \{L, M, G\}, \{M, G, R\}, \{G, C, B\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.5), \\
& (\{G, R, E, M\}, \{G, R, C, Ge, G\}, \{R, B\}, \{E, M, L\})(0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5), \\
& (\{M, Ge, E\}, \{B, G\}, \{E, M, L\}, \{R\})(0.5, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2), \\
& (\{G, M\}, \{C, M\}, \{Ge, E, C, R\}, \{M, C, G, B, L\}), \\
& (\{L, B, E, Ge\}, \{Ge, C, B\}, \{M, G\}, \{L, G\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2), \\
& (\{R, E, B\}, \{R, L\}, \{R, Ge\}, \{Ge, R, M\})(0.4, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6), \\
& (\{Ge, B\}, \{E, G\}, \{B, M, L\}, \{B, R\})(0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3), \\
& (\{G, E, Ge\}, \{C\}, \{E, R, M\}, \{G, B\}), \\
& (\{Ge, M, E\}, \{M, G\}, \{L, G\}, \{E, M, B, R\})(0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), \\
& (\{K, R, E\}, \{B, L, Ge\}, \{C, R, G\}, \{C, R\})(0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.4), \\
& (\{L, B, G\}, \{R, E, B\}, \{Ge, M, B\}, \{L, B, R\})(0.4, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3)}.
\end{aligned}$$

vi) The 'Pessimistic $\cap$ ' operation for $\check{C}_{n_1}$ ve $\check{C}_{n_2}$ is obtained from Definition 3.6 and similar to i such that

$$\begin{aligned}
\check{C}_{n_1} \check{\cap}_p \check{C}_{n_2} = & \{(\{G\}, \{R\}, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{L\}, \emptyset, \{G\}, \{C\})(0.3, 0.2, 0.1, 0.3), (\emptyset, \{G\}, \{C, R\}, \emptyset)(0.5, 0.5, 0.3, 0.4), \\
& (\{B\}, \{Ge, B\}, \{L, Ge\}, \{M, Ge\})(0.2, 0.5, 0.3, 0.6)\}, \\
& (\{E\}, \{M\}, \emptyset, \{B, G\}), (\{L\}, \emptyset, \{E\}, \emptyset)(0.2, 0.3, 0.3, 0.1), (\{G\}, \emptyset, \{C\}, \emptyset)(0.6, 0.3, 0.1, 0.7), \\
& (\{R\}, \emptyset, \{L\}, \{E, C\})(0.5, 0.4, 0.6, 0.2)\}, \\
& (\{E\}, \{Ge, E\}, \{C, B\}, \emptyset), (\emptyset, \{E, M\}, \emptyset, \{C, B\})(0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.5), (\emptyset, \{G\}, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.5, 0.4, 0.3, 0.5), \\
& (\emptyset, \{B\}, \emptyset, \{R\}) (0.5, 0.2, 0.3, 0.2)\}, \\
& (\{M\}, \{C\}, \{Ge, E, C\}, \emptyset), (\{B\}, \{C\}, \{M\}, \{L\})(0.3, 0.1, 0.3, 0.2), \\
& (\{R, E\}, \emptyset, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.4, 0.4, 0.3, 0.6), (\{Ge\}, \{E\}, \emptyset, \emptyset)(0.3, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3)\}, \\
& (\{G, E\}, \{C\}, \emptyset, \emptyset), (\{Ge, M\}, \emptyset, \{L, G\}, \{E\})(0.4, 0.3, 0.2, 0.1), \\
& (\{R\}, \{B\}, \{C\}, \{R\})(0.3, 0.4, 0.2, 0.4), (\emptyset, \{E\}, \{Ge, M\}, \{L\})(0.4, 0.4, 0.6, 0.3)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Abbreviations

NS: Neutrosophic Set

NQN: Neutrosophic Quadruple Number

NQS: Neutrosophic Quadruple Set

MVNS: Multi-Valued Neutrosophic Set

SVNQN: Set Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Number

SVNQS: Set Valued Neutrosophic Quadruple Set

GSVNQN: Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Number

GSVNQS: Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Set

MGSVNQN: Multiple Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Number

MGSVNQS: Multiple Generalized Set Valued Neutrosophic Quintuple Set

5. Conclusions

In this study, MGSVNQS and MGSVNQN are defined and their basic properties are given. For this reason, we have obtained a new structure for both MVNS and GSVNQSs. In addition, the operators of average union, average intersection, optimistic union, optimistic intersection, pessimistic union and pessimistic intersection are defined for this new structure. Thus, MGSVNQS can be used in decision-making applications by researchers. Also, researchers can be defined similarity and distance measure for MGSVNQSs.

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Received: March 23, 2024. Accepted: July 29, 2024